

DELAMINATION ANALYSIS FOR CROSS-PLY LAMINATES UNDER BENDING WITH CONSIDERATION OF CRACK FACE CONTACT AND FRICTION

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ABSTRACT

A finite element analysis of delamination crack growth for 2D- and 3D-models of two cross-ply laminated three-point bending specimens with different lay-ups is performed. For one of the 2D-cases contact and sliding friction along the crack faces has to be considered. From the 3D-analyses considerable 3D- and mode coupling effects are found along the crack front next to the free surface of the specimens.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced- and laminated composites have proved their usefulness and high potential through many applications in various fields. In particular in aircraft- and spacecraft structures components made from composite materials frequently are designed to withstand extreme loading conditions during service. Because in addition they have to meet strong fail-safe requirements, investigations of the failure behavior of composite materials and -structures are important subjects in materials- and engineering science. Among the various failure mechanisms that may develop in composite materials, like fibre- or matrix cracking and fibre debonding, interlaminar fracture or delamination is the major failure process in laminated composites. Delamination crack growth, which may initiate from manufacturing defects or from interlaminar shear- or bending cracks due to transversal static - or low velocity impact loading is widely under investigation now by means of analytical, numerical and experimental methods /1-4,6/.

In this paper the delamination crack growth in two cross-ply laminated three-point bending specimens with different laminate sequences (Fig. 1) is investigated. The finite element method (FEM) is used in combination with global- and local energy methods in order to calculate the strain energy release rates (SERRs) at the delamination crack tip of the 2D-models and along the delamination crack front through the thickness of the specimen for the 3D-model / 5,6/.

In the following section the numerical methods for the 2D- and 3D-fracture analyses will briefly be presented and discussed. In particular it will be shown that the straight forward and numerically highly effective Virtual Crack Closure Integral (VCCI)-method can also be utilised in the case of crack face contact and sliding friction along the crack faces /6/.

Fig. 1 Geometry of graphite/epoxy cross-ply laminated three point bending specimens

DELAMINATION ANALYSIS WITH CRACK FACE CONTACT AND FRICTION

According to IRWIN the total SERR G_T for quasi static crack extension in a brittle material can be defined on the basis of a global energy balance as follows

$$G_T(a) = -\frac{d\Pi(a)}{t da} = -\lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Pi(a + \Delta a) - \Pi(a)}{t\Delta a} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1) $\Pi=U-W$ is the total potential of the elastic body or structure, $U=1/2 \underline{u}^T \underline{K} \underline{u}$ is the elastic strain energy and $W = \underline{u}^T \underline{F}$ is the potential of the external loads (t thickness of the specimen). For a finite crack extension Δa it holds

$$-\frac{\Pi_j(a + \Delta a) - \Pi_j(a)}{t\Delta a} = G_T^{EN2} \left(a + \frac{\Delta a}{2} \right) \quad (2a)$$

or

$$-\Delta\Pi_{ij}^{global} = G_T^{EN2} \left(a + \frac{\Delta a}{2} \right) t\Delta a = W_{ij}^O, \quad (2b)$$

where W^O denotes the crack opening work. Because according to Eqs. (2a,b) two FE-analyses of the total body, with crack lengths a and $a+\Delta a$ are required, this approach is named global energy method here and is marked by the superscript EN2. From comparisons with reference solutions it is known that the global energy method EN2 is numerically highly accurate, even for rather coarse meshes, but as a disadvantage it has to be valued that by this approach the total SERR G_T^{EN2} can not be separated into the individual modes G_i , $i = I, II, III$ in cases of mixed-mode crack tip- or crack front conditions.

The global energy method can also be applied to crack face contact problems for coefficients of friction $\mu=0$, but for the generalised problem with contact and sliding friction along the crack faces Eq. (2b) has to be replaced by

$$-\Delta\Pi_{ij}^{global} = W_{ij}^O + W_{ij}^F. \quad (3)$$

The meaning of Eq. (3) is that in this case the change of total potential has to cover the energy for two different processes, namely the crack opening work W^O and the work W^F dissipated due to sliding friction along the crack faces. Thus at least one of the right hand side quantities has to be determined in addition, but preferably both and separately and independently, because then Eq. (3) will also provide a quantitative measure of accuracy for the different approaches that have been applied.

For fracture analysis problems where no crack face contact and friction is involved one can refer to IRWIN's basic idea, that for elastic bodies crack opening and crack closure are reversible processes. This means

$$W_{ij}^O = W_{ij}^C \quad (4)$$

is holding and consequently, instead of using Eq. (2b) in order to calculate W^O , we can utilise a local energy method, namely the VCCI- or 2C-method /5,6/ for computing the crack closure work W^C and the correlated total SERR G_T^{2C} . Thus with Eqs. (2a,b) we find

$$-\Delta \Pi_{ij}^{global} \stackrel{!}{=} W_{ij}^C \quad (5a)$$

and

$$G_T^{EN2} \left(a + \frac{\Delta a}{2} \right) \stackrel{!}{=} G_T^{2C} \left(a + \frac{\Delta a}{2} \right), \quad (5b)$$

where, respectively, the agreement between both sides of Eqs. (5a,b) provide a quantitative measure of accuracy for the different methods that have been applied.

Concerning the generalised problem to be solved here, the finding that the local energy method VCCI or 2C is also valid in the case of crack face contact and friction is a first important step to the solution. The second step is the finding that the work W^F , which is dissipated due to sliding friction along the crack faces during quasi static crack extension from crack length a to $a+\Delta a$, can be calculated by

$$W_{ij}^F = \frac{1}{2} C_x^{j-1}(a + \Delta a) \cdot \Delta u_x^{j-1}(a + \Delta a) + \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} \frac{1}{2} [C_x^{i-k}(a) + C_x^{j-(k+1)}(a + \Delta a)] \cdot [\Delta u_x^{j-(k+1)}(a + \Delta a) - \Delta u_x^{i-k}(a)] \quad (6)$$

In Eq. (6) the first term covers the friction work done by the first crack tip element during crack extension from a to $a+\Delta a$, whereas the second term is the sum of the work, which is dissipated due to sliding friction along the entire crack face contact zone. In Eq. (6) e.g. $C_x^{j-1}(a + \Delta a)$ denotes the tangential component of the contact force at a nodal point at a position $j-1$ and $\Delta u_x^{j-1}(a + \Delta a)$ is the relative tangential displacement between the correlated nodal points at the upper and lower crack faces. Thus for quasi static crack extension we find

$$-\Delta \Pi_{ij}^{global} \stackrel{!}{=} W_{ij}^C + W_{ij}^F, \quad (7)$$

where the quantitative agreement between both sides of Eq. (7) can be taken as a quantitative measure of accuracy for this approach, because all three quantities in Eq. (7) are computed separately and independently by different methods.

Because for the 3D-analyses the contact problem will only be solved for the case of neglectable friction ($\mu=0$), Eq. (7) reduces to Eq. (5a) again, due to $W^F = 0$ in this case.

SPECIMEN AND FE-MODEL

As already mentioned, for experimental investigations of the delamination behavior of laminated composites the three-point bending specimens as shown in Fig. 1 are frequently used, because as a function of laminate sequences the same transversal loading will create predominant mode I-or

mode II crack tip loading conditions, respectively (case 1 and 2). The two specimens under investigation are cross-ply laminates made from graphite/epoxy with a laminate sequence of [90₅/0₅/90₅] in case 1 and [0₅/90₅/0₅] in case 2. The relevant material-, geometrical- and loading parameters are given in Tab. 1. For the 2D-analysis plain strain conditions are assumed and due to the symmetry of the problem only one half of the specimen has to be modelled. The 2D FE-model of the specimen consists of 720 constant strain elements (CSE), with a mesh refinement in the region of delamination analysis that provides 4 CSE per laminate thickness and a step size of $\Delta a=0.2$ mm for the delamination crack extension steps, respectively. The FE-mesh of the 3D-models is assembled from 4320 8-node volume elements and is shown in Fig. 2. In the x,y-plane it is identical to the 2D-meshes but in the z-direction it contains 6 elements with a strong refinement adjacent to the free surface of the specimen.

TABLE 1 Material -, geometrical- and loading parameters of the specimen

E_{11}	=	119.9	GPa	h	=	2.187	mm
E_{22}, E_{33}	=	9.86	GPa	L	=	50.4	mm
G_{12}, G_{13}	=	5.24	GPa	t_{2D}	=	1.0	mm
G_{23}	=	3.52	GPa			(plane strain)	
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	=	0.3		t_{3D}	=	10.0	mm
ν_{23}	=	0.4		P	=	2.0	N/mm

Fig. 2 FE-mesh of the 3D-model of the specimen (one quarter with respect to symmetry)

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

From the deformed FE-mesh of the [90₅/0₅/90₅] laminate (case 1) in Fig. 3, and in particular from the mesh detail of the crack tip, a crack opening displacement can be detected. The quantitative results of the analysis in form of the SEERs G_i , $i = I, II$ and G_T are given in Fig. 4

Fig. 3 Undeformed and deformed FE-mesh of the specimens for case 1 and case 2

Fig. 4 Strain energy release rates for the [90₅/0₅/90₅] laminated specimen (case 1)

They confirm the mentioned crack tip behavior with a dominant SERR G_I but also a considerable G_{II} part. Furthermore decreasing G_i , $i = I, II$ and G_T values are found for increasing delamination crack lengths, which means a stable crack growth is found for case 1.

For the [0₅/90₅/0₅] laminate (case 2) from the FE-mesh in Fig. 3 and the crack tip detail only in-plane sliding displacements can be realised. This is confirmed by the SERRs, which are plotted for $\mu=0$ in Fig.5 and which show a highly predominant G_{II} with $G_{II} \approx G_T$ due to $G_I \approx 0$. But in contrast to case 1 increasing SERRs are found for longer delamination crack lengths, which means an unstable crack growth will occur when G_{II} reaches G_{IIc} .

With respect to the different approaches that are used in the numerical analysis the almost perfect agreement for all SERR results in Fig. 4 should be pointed out. This is due to the fine FE-mesh and the small crack extensions Δa , by which the deviations between the local energy method VCCI or 2C, which is numerically exact for a given finite Δa , and the approximative MVCCI or 1C approach according to RYBICKY and KANNINEN /5/ are vanishing. Furthermore the almost perfect agreement between the total SERRs G_T^{EN2} , as calculated by the global energy method EN2 from Eq. (2a), and G_T^{2C} in Fig. 5 should be mentioned.

Fig. 5 Strain energy release rates for the [0₅/90₅/0₅] lamin. specimen (case 2, contact sol., $\mu=0$)

Fig. 6 Effects of increasing coeff. of friction on the SERRs for short delaminations (case 2)

The same high level of agreement is also found with respect to Eq. (7) in the generalised case of sliding friction along the crack faces. Here the change in total potential $\Delta\Pi$ almost coincides with the sum of the independently calculated values of the crack closure work W^C and the sliding friction work W^F , respectively.

Furthermore a direct correlation between a growing amount of friction work W^F and a reduced level of crack closure work W^C , which is proportional to the total SERR in Fig. 6 is found, whereas the course of $\Delta\Pi$ versus a/L is found to be rather unaffected by increasing coefficients of friction.

By comparing Figs.6 and 8 it is found that for very short delamination crack lengths $0 \leq a/L \leq 0.05$ the total SERR G_T is considerably reduced with increasing coefficients of friction $0 \leq \mu \leq 0.8$, whereas for longer delaminations with $0.1 \leq a/L \leq 0.4$ hardly any effects with $\mu > 0$ are to be seen. These results become clear from Figs. 7 and 9 where the corresponding relative crack opening displacements are plotted, respectively. Only for very short delaminations with $0 \leq a/L \leq 0.05$ full contact and sliding friction for $\mu > 0$ along the crack faces is found (Fig. 7), whereas for $a/L > 0.05$ increasing crack opening directly behind the delamination crack tip develops, leaving only a few

Fig. 7 Relative normal crack face displacements for short delaminations (case 2)

Fig. 8 Effects of increasing coeff. of friction on the SERRs for longer delaminations (case 2)

elements in contact for $0.05 \leq a/L \leq 0.2$, and finally only one nodal point at the remote end of the crack faces for longer delaminations with $0.2 \leq a/L \leq 0.4$ (Fig. 9).

From these findings it fortunately can be concluded that investigations for determining the critical mode II SERR G_{IIc} experimentally are hardly affected by frictional effects ($G_{IIc} \approx G_{Tc}$ due to $G_I \approx 0$). Furthermore for the 3D-analyses the effects of sliding friction can be neglected here.

In Fig. 10 the findings from the 3D-analyses for cases 1 and 2 show that the SERRs $G_i(a, z/t)$, $i = I, II, III$ are about constant along a straight delamination crack front ($a = \text{const.}$) for normalised thickness coordinates $0 \leq z/t \leq 0.45$, but show remarkable 3D- and mode-coupling effects where the crack front meets the free surface of the specimen ($z/t \rightarrow 0.5$). For case 1 the predominant $G_I(a, z/t)$ decreases considerably for $z/t \rightarrow 0.5$, whereas G_{II} and the locally induced G_{III} show increasing values next to the free surface. Thus for the total SERR $G_T(a, z/t)$ the distribution as given in Fig. 10 is found, which means that fortunately the results from the 2D-analysis provide a conservative assessment in this case. But unfortunately this is not true for case 2 where for $z/t \rightarrow 0.5$ increasing values are found for all separated SERRs G_i , $i = I, II, III$, in particular for G_{II} , and consequently even more pronounced for the total SERR G_T .

Fig. 9 Relative normal crack face displacements for longer delaminations (case 2)

Fig. 10 Strain energy release rates for the 3D-model of cases 1 and 2 (contact solution, $\mu=0$)

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